

Helpdesk activity report

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1. Introduction

This deliverable is part of Task 5.3 “Development of a Helpdesk for supporting member in collaboration activities”. It consists in setting up a helpdesk that assists Signatory Members from the Startup Nations Standards (SNS) Declaration in fostering knowledge exchange. It will do so by addressing the countries’ enquiries and offer support through one-on-one interactions (via physical and digital channels) as well as other formats, such as webinars, trainings, and tutorials.

After several internal discussions, it was acknowledged that the term “helpdesk” may cause some confusion to prospective users. While it aims at offering advisory support, helpdesk tends to have a connotation related to customer service. It was therefore renamed “Service Line”. This term implies a broader scope and puts an emphasis on a long-term commitment to supporting the Signatory Members. It will henceforth be used throughout this report and other documents drafted by ESNA going forward.

This report serves as a review of the first activities carried out under the scope of the Service Line.

2. Service Line Design and Structure

Monitoring the progress of the 8 Startup Nations Standards is part of ESNA’s strategic objectives, and the Service Line is a key enabler to increase the implementation level of the Standards by countries. By individually assisting ESNA Members in improving the Standards, it facilitates knowledge sharing and collaboration between countries.

Halfway through the project, the ESNA Team met and brainstormed several times to outline and finalise the content and shape of the Service Line concept. These discussions were based on previous experiences with the pilots and the requirements previously laid out.

Based on the results of the pilots carried out to test the concept (in-depth description may be found in the section below), the Service Line was officially launched on the 30th of April 2024 by email to the whole Focal Points network¹ (See Appendix). After this formal announcement, the ESNA Team sent out an information email including a brief description of the service, as well as an option to fill out a quick Expression of Interest should a Focal Point wish to meet with ESNA to discuss specific potential collaboration further, under the Service Line (See Appendix).

The aforementioned initiatives are based on past pilots and may later encompass a broader range of activities should it be relevant for the beneficiaries. The portfolio may also expand as ESNA grows, and its related objectives may be adjusted for 2025.

¹ The ESNA’s Focal Point network is composed by the official contact person in each of the ESNA’s Signatory Members.

3. Service Line’s Pilots

In order to better grasp the needs of the Signatory Countries, a total of six pilots were carried out between June 2023 and March 2024. They came in various shapes and were an opportunity to refine the concept of the Service Line. More details on these pilots may be found below. Please note that as this deliverable is public, some information such as the countries’ names may not be disclosed.

Pilot 1

- Timeframe: June 2023
- Context: Learn about another country’s ecosystem mapping
- Activity: Member State A demonstrated particular interest in Member State B’s innovation and startup ecosystem mapping. ESNA served as an intermediary so that both countries could meet and dig deeper on this topic.
- Deliverable: Identifying the main actors and putting both parties in contact via email

Pilot 2

- Timeframe: September 2023
- Context: Ecosystem contacts in another country
- Activity: Member State A enquired about potential collaboration with Member State B’s official representatives on startup ecosystem topics. ESNA served as an intermediary so that both countries could meet and build bridges.
- Deliverables: Email with list of contacts and outreach to local Focal Point

Pilot 3

- Timeframe: November 2023
- Context: Startup definition by another country
- Activity: Member State A enquired about Country B’s national startup definition. ESNA reached out to Member State B’s Focal Points in order to get a translation of the national law, which was later shared with Country A.
- Deliverables: Email and outreach to local Focal Point

Pilot 4

- Timeframe: December 2023
- Context: Regulatory sandbox analysis
- Activity: A Focal Point enquired about the concept of regulatory sandboxes and wished to find out more about it. ESNA suggested a discovery meeting with the main stakeholders to share and discuss some insights.
- Deliverable: Discovery meeting

Pilot 5

- Timeframe: January 2024
- Context: Country overview and recommendations based on SNS Report 2023 (draft version)
- Activity: A country Government enquired about the results of the SNS Report 2023 analysis. The ESNA team prepared a short report indicating the country's strengths and weaknesses, including some recommendations and best practices. It was then presented to government officials, resulting in a concrete set of actions.
- Deliverables: A report and in-person discussion of the results
- Main highlights: Call to action to increase mainly the implementation level of "Fast startup creation", "Innovation in Regulation", "Innovation in Procurement", "Access to finance" and "Social Inclusion and Diversity". Additionally, it was recommended to carry out an impact assessment of the Stock Options scheme.

Pilot 6

- Timeframe: March 2024
- Context: Mapping regulatory sandboxes across the EU
- Activity: A Government enquired about regulatory sandboxes, and how their country positioned itself in this regard. The ESNA Team therefore developed a document defining this concept and the various types of sandboxes, the role of startups, as well as the current state of play at national and European levels.
- Deliverables: Discovery meeting and a report
- Main highlights: some European Sandboxes can be more focused on analysing certain regulation, while others can be more focused on developing specific solutions; involvement of a variety of stakeholders in Regulatory

Sandboxes is fundamental; concerning startup-oriented solutions, should be considered legal frameworks facilitating startup participation and its financial support for experimentation.

During the pilot phase, the requests came either informally – e.g. during a face-to-face interaction – or in a more formal way, typically via email.

This series of pilots was equally beneficial to the Focal Points and to the ESNA Team. National Governments had the opportunity to gather relevant insights and access knowledge and benchmarking to support their policy-making process, while ESNA had the chance to refine the concept of a Service Line.

Considering the number of pilots that occurred with no specific promotion, ESNA is now confident that there is a strong need for such a service, and that this support will be of value to the Signatory Countries. It strengthened the idea that the Service Line may eventually become a reference point for all European policymakers. The current expressions of interest system created after the official announcement allows the ESNA Team to manage the pipeline of enquiries. In just the first two weeks, there are already two requests in the pipeline.

4. Assessment and Next Steps

Due to the time policy implementation requires, it is challenging to accurately evaluate the concrete results of the Service Line pilots as of today. The team has prepared a survey (See Appendix) to assess the quality of its service and identify potential opportunities to further collaborate with the Signatory Members. Additionally, team members will be responsible for regularly following up with the Service Line beneficiaries to assess the Service Line's impact. In addition, the future editions of the Scoreboard will be a way to understand if the first projects tackled by the Service Line had a short/mid-term impact.

The process is already well underway, as some Focal Points have already expressed interest following the pilots and/or the informational email (See Appendix). Although requests have been received on an ad hoc basis, the Service Line will be consistently promoted whenever opportunities arise.

5. Conclusions

Task 5.3 “Development of a Helpdesk for supporting members in collaboration activities” stemming from this project has enabled ESNA to set up the framework of its Service Line and test out its relevance through the first pilots.

The Service Line plays an instrumental role in ESNA's commitment to support Governments fostering startup-friendly policies in Europe. With six pilots, it had a positive start before its official launch in April 2024. These first exercises helped shape the format of the Service Line and highlighted a need for such a service from the Signatory Countries. The Service Line is now officially launched and has already generated significant interest.

ESNA expects the Service Line to become one of its flagship projects by improving national policy frameworks of the Member States. The Service Line is in keeping with ESNA's overarching mission to bring Europe to the lead of global startup ecosystem.

6. Appendix

Service Line launch email

Dear ESNA Members,

We are launching the ESNA Service Line, an initiative to benefit your country's startup ecosystem. Starting in May, ESNA will offer personalized support, analysis, and reporting to help countries like yours strengthen the startup ecosystem by deep diving into Startup Nation Standards results and best practises.

What is the Service Line?

The Service Line is an advisory system explicitly designed for ESNA members seeking guidance, recommendations, or technical information on implementing the game-changing 8 Startup Nations Standards. We understand that each country has unique needs, so our support will be tailored to individual requests, offering solutions such as benchmarking, mapping ecosystems, and high-level recommendations provided through a report, presentation or other format agreed upon during the alignment phase.

Why does it matter?

ESNA is committed to monitoring national policies through its annual Startup Nations Standards Report. With this system, we will actively support countries like yours in enhancing the implementation of the 8 policy dimensions. Our team has a unique European-wide advantage point and a deep understanding of the European startup policy landscape to provide valuable insights and recommendations.

What are some of the examples of Service Line?

ESNA has already delivered a number of ad hoc services to its members, covering topics such as identifying areas of improvement on the Startup Nations Standards, benchmarking regulatory sandboxes across Europe, or providing information on existing startup laws in other countries.

How does it work?

Email standards.policy@esnalliance.eu with a brief description of your request. Our team will work with you to define the scope, deliverables, and timeline and discuss the appropriate support formats, such as exploratory meetings, targeted reports, or results presentations.

We encourage you to take advantage of this opportunity, look forward to hearing from you, and support your journey toward a thriving startup ecosystem.

Service Line informational email

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Europe
Startup
Nations
Alliance

Welcome to ESNA Service Line

The Service Line developed by ESNA's Standards & Policy Department, has now been officially launched. It aims to support your country in developing innovation policies and implement the #8 Startup Nation Standards.

How does it work?

Following up on the latest information sent by ESNA team, we would like to provide you with some more practical information on how the service line will operate.

1. Reach ESNA

Reach our team by email or fill out our contact form

2. Kick-off Meeting

Introductory and exploratory meeting with ESNA team to present the country's challenges and needs

3. Report Delivery

ESNA team will deliver a report tailored to your country needs addressing the topics under discussion

4. Discussion Meeting

Final meeting to present and discuss the results

5. Feedback

A feedback form will be sent in order to understand whether the objectives were met and how we can improve.

Expression of Interest in Service Line

Service Line - expression of interest

This form aims to collect non-binding expressions of interest about the Service Line.

Start press Enter ↵
⌚ Takes 1 minute

Cover of the Expression of Interest to be submitted by interested Member States

Service Line, from pilot to launch

Service Line Feedback Survey

Service Line Feedback Survey

The following questionnaire aims to evaluate the services provided by ESNA's Standards & Policy department. We therefore thank you in advance for taking the time to support us improving ESNA's Service Line.

⌚ Takes 2 minutes

Cover of the Feedback Survey to be answered by the stakeholders involved in each request

